

INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES OF DEVELOPING
SPECIFIC COMPETENT SKILL OF TEACHERS OF BOL AJAK
TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

Hajikarimova Gulasal Tadjialiyevna

teacher of the technological education department of Fergana State University

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Abstract: In this article formation of pedagogical potential of students, application of modern pedagogical technologies to the educational process based on the competence approach, use of information and communication technologies in the course of the lesson, preparation and implementation of state education standards at the level of developed countries, knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, activation of competencies is given.

Key words: Technology, teacher, innovation, competence, training.

Enter. From the first years of independence, the development of the education system in our country has been raised to the level of state policy, ensuring that our children acquire modern knowledge and skills in conditions corresponding to world standards, and grow up to be physically and spiritually mature people. Great work is being done to realize the abilities and talents, intellectual potential, to develop the feelings of loyalty and self-sacrifice in the hearts of our youth. The Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev on April 20, 2017 - on measures to further develop the higher education system is a logical continuation of the ongoing work on reforming the education system in our country, as well as taking it to a new stage. It is important because it aims to raise. One of the most important aspects of the decision, in which special attention is paid to the observance of the criteria of international standards in the training of highly qualified specialists, the creation of conditions at its level, the training of personnel with modern knowledge and skills in accordance with the spirit and demand.[2]

In order to create an innovative educational environment based on the competence approach, first of all, students are required to familiarize themselves with the scientific and technical innovations of recent years and regularly study the problems of implementation.

As a result of creating an innovative educational environment in the teaching process, firstly, the process of students' introduction to the pedagogical process is accelerated, secondly, the student's pedagogical skills are formed, and thirdly, the student's enthusiasm for pedagogical professions increases [3]

It consists in developing the professional training of future technology teachers, expanding their pedagogical thinking, and forming methodological knowledge and skills necessary for the use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching science. The technology of preparing future technology teachers for innovative activities is one of the important issues today. Innovations mean the use of achievements (discoveries, inventions, scientific and construction projects, etc.) achieved by the human mind to increase efficiency in one or another field of activity, respectively, innovations are technological, economic, environmental, management, military, political, socio-cultural, legal and divided into other types. The world of innovation is as colorful and diverse as the fields of human activity. The power of innovations provides great opportunities in protecting society's lifestyle, health, and increasing its scientific potential. Innovation (eng. innovations — introduced innovation, invention) — 1) funds spent on the economy to ensure replacement of technology and technology generations; innovations in the fields of technology, technology, management and labor organization based on scientific and technical achievements and best practices, as well as their application in various fields and spheres of activity.[7] Educational technology- is used to define the scientific aspect of innovative technology. It is a systematic way of creating, applying and determining all processes of teaching and knowledge acquisition, taking into account technical and human resources and their cooperation, which sets the task of optimizing educational forms. Today, in the scientific and popular literature, we can find different classifications when defining the concept of "Innovative technology". According to Uzbek scientist N. Sayidakhmedov: "Innovative technology is the influence of the teacher (educator) on students with the help of teaching (educational) tools and the formation of predetermined personal qualities in them as a product of this activity. is a process" "Innovative technology - on the basis of systematic, technological approaches to facilitate the forms of education, to guarantee the result and to objectively evaluate the interaction of human potential and technical means, clarifying the educational goals, teaching and knowledge is a set of methods and techniques used in the processes of mastering". He considers innovative technology as a method of education, in a certain sense, a set of educational processes, tools, forms and methods. "Innovative technology is a system of developing and improving educational processes, content, methods and tools of education based on objective laws of education and diagnostic goals." At each stage of teaching the tasks of innovative technology as a science, defining the content of education, preparing the forms

and tools of education, preparing situational texts and tests to be included in the content of the subject, developing professional qualities and moral qualities in a person. development of a system of tasks aimed at mastering, determination of the result of education and level of mastering, preparation of test tasks for their objective assessment.[8] Innovation is the result of scientific and creative activity aimed at creating new techniques and technologies, developing improved methods and forms of work activity management, and introducing them in order to increase efficiency in one or another field of activity. Since innovation means using the achievements of the human mind (discovery, invention, scientific and construction projects, etc.) to increase efficiency in one or another field of activity, respectively, innovations are technological, economic, environmental, management, military, political, socio-cultural, legal and divided into other species. The world of innovation is as varied and varied as the fields of human activity. The power of innovations provides great opportunities in protecting society's lifestyle, health, and increasing its scientific potential. Wide and effective use of innovations in this regard. The advantages of innovative technologies are that they lead to better mastering of the teaching content; - provision of timely communications; - creation of conditions for putting concepts into practice; - offering various forms of teaching methods; - high level of motivation; - remember the material well; - improvement of communication skills; - growth of self-esteem; - positive attitude of students to the content of the subject, to the learning process; - development of critical and logical thoughts, not only helping to master the content; - formation of problem solving skills. Disadvantages of innovative technologies are time-consuming; - students are not always able to control properly; - the teacher's role is low, even when learning very complex material; - Because they are "weak" students, "strong" students also receive low grades.[5] Stages and tasks of cooperative teaching technologies in technology lessons. Cooperative teaching technologies are formed on the basis of cooperative pedagogy, which differs from traditional pedagogy as follows: In traditional education, the teacher is considered the subject of the pedagogical process, and the student is the object. In cooperative pedagogy, the student is considered as the subject of his educational activity. In this, the teacher and the student become equal as subjects of the pedagogical process, and the process of cooperative pedagogy is formed. They will be mutual partners, friends, co-creators, co-participants, sympathizers, co-leaders. Cooperation relations are established between teachers, administration and student and teacher organizations, leaders, parents, and the public.

Collaborative pedagogy ensures the achievement of high results by developing the student's motivations and humanizing the educational process. Collaborative teaching allows to achieve the following results: -enriches the student's learning process: -gives students a set of cognitive information that is distributed among them; - makes students eager to learn the material; - expands students' opportunities to form their own personal knowledge and outlook; —increases the efficiency of two-way exchange of information; -gives students the necessary knowledge to prepare for independent life; — promotes positive interactions between different cultures and socio-economic groups.

summary , the stages and tasks of collaborative teaching technologies in technology lessons. Cooperative teaching technologies will be formed on the basis of cooperative pedagogy. It differs from traditional pedagogy as follows, and is a collection of works aimed at improving innovative activity.

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